

Clinicopathological Analysis of 502 Patients with Oral Squamous Cell Carcinoma with Special Interest to Distant Metastasis

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Oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) is the most common malignancy of the oral cavity. Distant metastasis (DM) especially bone metastasis (BM) may reduce patients' quality of life and affects the clinical outcome. We performed clinicopathological analysis of 502 patients with OSCC undergoing radical surgery in order to evaluate the correlation values of clinicopathological features for OSCC with special interest in DM. DM was found in 54 cases and among them 44 and 25 cases had pulmonary metastasis (PM) and BM, respectively. Advanced T stage, positive N stage, lower histologic grade and higher score YK classification were the independent significant prognostic factors found in our series of 502 cases of OSCC. Positive lymph node was the most important prognostic factors in DM and BM; on the other hand, in PM, it was lower histological grade. All patients with BM except one had vertebral bone metastasis. These characteristics of DM, including BM and PM, of OSCC are useful for understanding the metastatic process of OSCC.

Key words: distant metastasis, bone metastasis, oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC), prognostic factors

INTRODUCTION

Oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) is the most common malignancy of the oral cavity, causing more deaths than any other oral disease [1]. In the middle of the 20th century, it was reported that 48% of patients with OSCC presented distant metastasis (DM) within 9 months of treatment and 80% within 2 years (Data from 1943 to 1978) [2]. During the era of multidisciplinary therapy of surgery, radiation and chemotherapy for patients with advanced stage, it was reported that 20–23% of patients who received radiotherapy or combined therapy had DM (from 1995 to 2000) [3]. Although the frequency of DM of OSCC actually decreased, we still need to pay attention to DM of OSCC because it reduces patients' quality of life (QOL) and affects the clinical outcome. For patients of OSCC, knowing the prognostic factors for DM could be an important tool for predicting their prognosis and proposing additional treatment.

Many factors such as clinicopathologic parameters, angiogenesis, metastasis-related genes and gene-products, and individual immune status can influence DM of OSCC. Clinical T and N stages, histologic grade, loco-regional control, presence of extra-capsular spread (ECS), number of pathologic lymph nodes, and number of levels with pathologic lymph node, have been found to be associated with DM in the previous series [4–9]. However, there has been no report about bone metastasis (BM) of OSCC to date. BM of OSCC seems to be one of the important problems for patients' QOL.

In this article, we performed clinicopathological analyses of 502 cases of OSCC in order to identify clinicopathological features of OSCC and tried to make special interest to DM including BM.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

Patients and samples

Medical records of patients who underwent surgical resection in the Department of Oral Maxillofacial Surgery, Tokai University Hospital from 1996 to 2007 were retrieved from the electronic medical record system. A total of 502 cases received radical surgical resection with curative intent and histopathological diagnosis of OSCC. Patients who had any previous malignancy were excluded. Cases with DM prior to surgery were excluded. Of the 502 patients, 160 patients received preoperative chemotherapy because of the rapid growth of tumor previous to surgical resection. Postoperative radiotherapy to the primary site was performed in the patients that had residual tumor at the surgical margins; radiotherapy on the neck was performed in patients with pathologic N2b-2c and N3 stage or in patients of extra-capsular spread of lymph nodes. Fifty-nine patients received postoperative radiotherapy according to the protocol of our department [10], 78 patients received postoperative chemotherapy and 301 patients underwent surgery alone. The protocol of medical treatment for OSCC in our department had not been changed during 1996 to 2007. The observation period was from 1 month to 204 months with a median of 65 months. DM followed the definition of the WHO TNM classification of carcinomas of the oral

Fig. 1 Hematoxylin-Eosin stain.
(a) well differentiation (b) moderately differentiation (c) poorly differentiation

cavity [11]. DM is exclusive of regional cervical lymph nodes and direct invasion from carcinoma. After surgery, routine follow-up included monthly clinical examinations in the first year and bimonthly clinical examinations thereafter for up to 5 years. Lost to follow up were 20 cases (3.9%) until 5 years. DM including BM was diagnosed by Ultrasound, X-ray, CT Scan, MRI Scan, ^{99m}Tc scintigraphy, and/or FDG-PET.

Clinical information of age, sex, pT stage and pN stage at radical surgery were investigated. The clinical staging and TNM classification were determined according to the International Union against Cancer (IUCC) [12]. The pT stage was sub-classified into the pT1 (tumor size ≤ 2 cm), pT2 (2–4 cm), pT3 (> 4 cm) and pT4 (invades adjacent structures) categories. The pN stage was sub-classified into the pN0 (No regional lymph node metastasis), pN1 (a single ipsilateral ≤ 3 cm), pN2 (a single ipsilateral 3–6 cm, in multiple ipsilateral ≤ 6 cm, in bilateral or contralateral ≤ 6 cm) and pN3 (> 6 cm) categories

This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Institutional Review Board (IRB) for Clinical Research at Tokai University School of Medicine (09R-003). Informed consent was provided in compliance with the Helsinki Declaration. Patient anonymity was preserved.

Histological characteristics

Tissue samples were fixed in formalin and embed-

ded in paraffin by routine methods. The histological grades of OSCC were assessed under haematoxylin-eosin representative tissue sections and re-classified into well, moderately, and poorly differentiated subgroups by the World Health Organization (Fig.1) [11] and mode of invasion by YK classification (Fig.2) [13]. YK classification is modification of the Jacobsson criteria [14] to evaluate the mode of invasion of the tumor-host borderline grade 1, well defined borderline; grade 2, cords, less marked borderline; grade 3, groups of cells and no distinct borderline; and grade 4, diffuse invasion. Grade 4 was further sub-classified into grades 4C and 4D. Grade 4C showed diffuse invasion of cord-like type; tumor cells of this type invade deeply as cord- or round-shaped micro tumor nests. Grade 4D showed diffuse invasion of wide-spread type; tumor cells of this type, either singly or a few at a time, invade diffusely into the deepest portion of the tumor. As described by Yamamoto E. *et al.*, the YK classification correlates with the survival of the patients: a higher YK grade of invasion is associated with worsening prognosis in OSCC [14,15].

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS analytics software 22.0 version. Statistical significance was defined as P -value < 0.05. Clinicopathological and immunohistochemical features (age, sex, pT stage, pN stage, histological grade, and YK classification) were

Fig. 2 YK classification. (a) grade 1, well defined borderline (b) grade 2, cords, less marked borderline (c) grade 3, groups of cells and no distinct borderline (d) grade 4c, showed diffuse invasion of cord-like type (e) grade 4D, showed diffuse invasion of wide-spread

compared using the non-parametric Chi-Square test. The comparison included that between the DM group and the non-distant-metastasis (N-DM) group. Only significant variables in the univariate analyses were supplied into the binary logistic regression analysis for the identification of the best predictors for DM. Overall survival (OS) curves were calculated from the date of surgery to the date of death or last follow-up. For disease-specific survival (DDS) curves, patients who died from causes other than OSCC were censored at the time of death. Cox proportional-hazards regression for survival data analysis, univariate and multivariate, was performed to explore the relationship between the survival of the patients and several explanatory variables. Survival curves were plotted by the Kaplan-Meier method and log-rank test.

RESULTS

Clinicopathological features of patients

The clinicopathological features of the 502 patients are shown in Table 1a. The age of the patients ranged from 19 years to 96 years with a median age of 64

years. Patients older than 60 years were 324 (64.5%). The male to female ratio was 293:209. The most frequent primary location was the tongue: 232 patients (46.2%), followed by lower gingiva: 117 patients (23.3%), floor of the mouth: 49 patients (9.8%), upper gingiva: 43 patients (8.6%), buccal mucosa: 36 cases (7.2%) and other region: 25 patients (4.9%).

DM was found in 54 cases (10.8%) and metastatic sites were as follows: lung, 44 cases; bone, 25 cases; mediastinum (soft tissue), 10 cases; liver, 9 cases; kidney, 3 cases; brain, 2 cases; spleen, 2 cases and adrenal gland, 2 cases. Multiple metastases were found in 32 cases. Among 25 cases with BM, 19 cases had metastasis in vertebrae bone (lumbar vertebrae, 13 cases; thoracic vertebrae, 9 cases; cervical vertebrae, 2 cases), 7 cases in rib, 4 cases in clavicle, 2 cases in thigh bone and 2 cases in temporal bone. Among 54 cases with DM, it was found from 1 month to 76 months with a median of 11 months after radical surgery. Survival duration after DM was from 1 to 21 months with a median of 3 months. Twenty-nine cases (29/54 53.7%) were found in loco-regional recurrence. Among 25 cases with BM,

Table 1a Clinicopathological and immunohistochemical features in 502 patients with OSCC.

variable	Distant metastasis		P^\dagger	O/R
	All cases n = 502 (%)	Present n = 54 (%)		
Age				
< 60	178 (35.5%)	17 (31.5%)	161 (35.9%)	0.518
≥ 60	324 (64.5%)	37 (68.5%)	287 (64.1%)	
Sex				
M	293 (58.4%)	30 (55.6%)	263 (58.7%)	0.657
F	209 (41.6%)	24 (44.4%)	185 (41.3%)	
pT stage				
T1, T2	315 (62.7%)	22 (40.7%)	293 (65.4%)	< 0.001
T3, T4	187 (37.3%)	32 (59.3%)	155 (34.6%)	2.75 (1.55-4.90)
pN stage				
N0	353 (70.3%)	18 (33.3%)	335 (74.8%)	< 0.001
N1, N2, N3	149 (29.7%)	36 (66.7%)	113 (25.2%)	5.93 (3.24-10.85)
Histological grade				
Well, Moderate	470 (93.6%)	45 (83.3%)	425 (94.9%)	< 0.001
Poor	32 (6.4%)	9 (16.7%)	23 (5.1%)	3.70 (1.61-8.07)
YK classification				
Grade 1, 2	87 (17.3%)	2 (3.7%)	80 (17.9%)	0.008
Grade 3, 4C, 4D	415 (82.7%)	52 (96.3%)	368 (82.1%)	5.65 (1.33-23.64)

OSCC: oral squamous cell carcinoma, P : P value, O/R: odds ratios, M: male, F: female, pT: pathology primary tumor, pN: pathology lymph node metastasis, YK classification; Yamamoto-Kohama classification, \dagger : Chi-square test

Table 1b Associations between pulmonary metastasis with the clinicopathological and immunohistochemical features in 502 patients with OSCC.

variable	pulmonary metastasis		P^\dagger	O/R
	Present n = 44 (%)	Absence n = 458 (%)		
Age				
< 60	15 (34.1%)	163 (35.6%)	0.492	
≥ 60	29 (65.9%)	295 (64.4%)		
Sex				
M	22 (50.0%)	271 (59.2%)	0.154	
F	22 (50.0%)	187 (40.8%)		
pT stage				
T1, T2	17 (38.6%)	298 (65.1%)	0.001	2.96
T3, T4	27 (61.4%)	160 (34.9%)		(1.57-5.6)
pN stage				
N0	17 (38.4%)	336 (73.4%)	< 0.001	4.37
N1, N2, N3	27 (61.4%)	122 (26.6%)		(2.3-8.31)
histological grade				
Well, Moderate	35 (79.5%)	435 (95.0%)	0.001	4.86
Poor	9 (20.5%)	23 (5.0%)		(2.09-11.31)
YK classification				
Grade 1, 2	1 (2.3%)	81 (17.7%)	0.003	9.24
Grade 3, 4C, 4D	43 (97.7%)	377 (82.3%)		(1.25-68.07)

OSCC: oral squamous cell carcinoma, P : P value, O/R: odds ratios, M: male, F: female, pT: pathology primary tumor, pN: pathology lymph node metastasis, YK classification; Yamamoto-Kohama classification, \dagger : Chi-square test

14 cases (56%) had local recurrence.

Clinical outcome of patients with OSCC

OS curves are shown in Fig. 3. The median OS in the study was 68 months, with 188 deaths, of which 112

were because of OSCC. The 5-year OS with T1-2 and T3-4 was 83.6% and 49.6%, respectively. There was a statistically significant difference between patients with T1-2 and those with T3-4 ($P < 0.001$). The 5-year OS was 84.6% for the pathologically node-negative

Table 1c Associations between bone metastasis with the clinicopathological and immunohistochemical features in 502 patients with OSCC.

variable	Bone metastasis		<i>P</i> [†]	O/R
	Present n = 25 (%)	Absence n = 477 (%)		
Age				
< 60	5 (20.0%)	173 (36.3%)	0.097	
≥ 60	20 (80.0%)	304 (63.7%)		
Sex				
M	17 (68.0%)	276 (57.9%)	0.316	
F	8 (32.0%)	201 (42.1%)		
pT stage				
T1, T2	13 (52.0%)	302 (63.3%)	0.254	
T3, T4	12 (48.0%)	175 (36.7%)		
pN stage				
N0	6 (24.0%)	347 (72.7%)	< 0.001	8.54
N1, N2, N3	19 (76.0%)	130 (27.3%)		(3.30–21.63)
histological grade				
Well, Moderate	20 (80.0%)	450 (94.3%)	< 0.001	4.17
Poor	5 (20.0%)	27 (5.7%)		(1.45–11.96)
YK classification				
Grade 1, 2	1 (4.0%)	81 (17.0%)	0.049	4.91
Grade 3, 4C, 4D	24 (96.0%)	396 (83.0%)		(0.66–36.81)

OSCC: oral squamous cell carcinoma, *P*: *P* value, O/R: odds ratios, M: male, F: female, pT: pathology primary tumor, pN: pathology lymph node metastasis, YK classification; Yamamoto-Kohama classification, † : Chi-square test

pN0 group and 62.6% for the pN+ group ($P < 0.001$) (Fig. 3b). It was 70.7% for well and moderately and 34.4% for poorly ($P < 0.001$) (Fig. 3c); 90.1% in YK-classification 1-2 and 64% in 3, 4C and 4D ($P < 0.001$) (Fig. 3d); 73.7% for non-pulmonary-metastasis (N-PM) and 13.6% for pulmonary metastasis (PM) ($P < 0.001$) (Fig. 3e); 71.4% for N-BM and 12% for BM ($P < 0.001$) (Fig. 3f).

The Cox proportional-hazards ratios, univariate and multivariate, are present in Table 2 for both OS and DSS. In the univariate analysis all variables but sex and age retained the prognostic value as explanatory variables ($P < 0.05$); among them pN stage had the highest Hazard Ratio (HR = 2.631) for OS whereas in YK for DSS (HR = 6.262), YK-classification had prognostic relevance in concordance to previous report [14,15].

Evaluation between DM and N-DM groups

Significant differences in pT stage, pN stage, histological grade and YK classification were found between the DM group (54 cases) and N-DM group (448 cases, Table 1a). Advanced pT stage, positive pN stage, poorly (low grade) differentiated and high grade (diffuse type) of YK classification were related to the presence of DM ($P < 0.05$). These 4 variables with significance in the univariate analyses were entered into the binary logistic regression analysis; and only pN stage and histological grade retained the significance value as prognostic factors. Of note, positive pN was the highest prognostic factor for the presence of DM (OR = 4.562) (Table 3). The presence of DM was associated with worsening overall survival of the patients, Hazard Risk (HR) 5.960 (95% CI, 4.27–8.32; $P < 0.001$).

Evaluation between pulmonary PM and N-PM groups

Significant differences were found in pT, pN stage, histological grade and YK classification between the PM group (44 cases) and N-PM group (458 cases, Table 1b). Advanced pT stage, positive pN stage, poor histological grades (low grade) and high grade (diffuse type) of YK classification were progressively related to the presence of PM ($P < 0.05$). Through binary logistic regression, only the variables of pN stage and histological grades retained the significance value as prognostic factors. Of note, the histological grades (low grade) was the highest prognostic factors for the presence of PM (OR = 4.276) (Table 3).

Evaluation between BM and N-BM groups

Significant differences in pN stage, histological grade and YK classification were found between the BM group (25 cases) and N-BM group (477 cases, Table 1c). Positive pN stage, poor histological grades (low grade) and high grade (diffuse type) of YK classification were progressively related to the presence of BM ($P < 0.05$). Through binary logistic regression, only the variables of pN stage and histological grade, retained the significance value as prognostic factors. Of note, the positive pN was the highest prognostic factor for the presence of BM (OR = 5.198) (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

We performed clinicopathological analysis of 502 cases with OSCC in order to identify clinicopathological features of OSCC with special interest to DM. In this study, the 5-year survival rate was 68.4%. Among all patients, the prognosis of patients with preoperative chemotherapy was poorer than that of patients with-

Fig. 3 Overall survival curves for: (a) T stage, (b) N stage, (c) histological grade, (d) YK classification, (e) pulmonary metastasis and (f) bone metastasis.

out preoperative chemotherapy. In patients in pN2-3, no different clinical outcome between patients with or without preoperative chemotherapy was found, but the performance of postoperative chemotherapy and/or RT resulted in improved clinical evolution (DDS, $P < 0.05$). We may consider preoperative chemotherapy is less effective in these patients.

DM occurred in about 10% of patients with OSCC from 1 month to 76 months after radical surgery in a median observation term of 11 months. The survival term of the patients with DM ranged from 1 to 21 months after metastasis. More than half of the patients (29/54, 53.7%) in the DM group presented loco-regional recurrence and they show better prognosis than those with the absence of loco-regional recurrence. Among 29 cases with local recurrence, 16 cases received tumor excision, chemotherapy and/or radiotherapy and 13 cases did supportive palliation. The survival time after local recurrence ranged from 1 to 30 months (median of 9 months) and 1 to 20 months (median of 6 months), respectively. Additional therapy may affect better prognosis. Among 54 cases with

DM, comparison between the local recurrence group (29 cases) and no local recurrence group (25 cases) showed no significant difference in age, sex, pT stage, pN stage, histological grade and YK-classification. But it is interesting that time to DM was shorter in the no local recurrence group (from 1 month to 76 months with a range of 17 months in the local recurrence group vs. 3 months to 29 months with a range of 9 months in the no local recurrence group) ($P < 0.05$). We suspect that the direction of group which a local recurrence does not accept involved and this participated in prognosis early intentionally. It is interesting that the histological grades and pN were the highest prognostic factors for the presence of PM and BM, respectively. The reason is unknown; it may be the result of a different metastatic mechanism.

We found BM in 5% (25/502) of OSCC and in 46.2% (25/54) of DM. In our series, the survival term of the patients with BM ranged from 1 to 6 months with 2.32 months on average. The frequency of BM is reported to be 65-70% in breast cancer, 65-70% in prostatic cancer, 60% in thyroid carcinoma, 40% in

Table 2 COX regression analysis of various factors for OSCC prognosis.

variable	unfavorable/favorable	Overall Survival			
		Univariate Analysis		Multivariate Analysis	
		HR (95% CI)	<i>P</i>	HR (95% CI)	<i>P</i>
pN stage	N1, N2, N3/ N0	3.799 (2.844–5.074)	< 0.001	2.631 (1.931–3.584)	< 0.001
Histological grade	Poor/ Well, Moderate	2.397 (1.520–3.780)	< 0.001	2.080 (1.313–3.293)	0.020
pT stage	T3, T4/T1, T2	2.824 (2.115–3.771)	< 0.001	1.992 (1.463–2.713)	< 0.001
Age	≥60/ <60	1.897 (1.365–2.637)	< 0.001	1.790 (1.285–2.494)	0.001
YK classification	Grade 3, 4C, 4D/1, 2	2.566 (1.537–4.285)	< 0.001	1.613 (0.948–2.744)	0.078
Sex	M/ F	1.104 (0.825–1.479)	0.056		

variable	unfavorable/favorable	Disease-Specific Survival			
		Univariate Analysis		Multivariate Analysis	
		HR(95% CI)	<i>P</i>	HR(95% CI)	<i>P</i>
YK classification	Grade 3, 4C, 4D/1, 2	12.883 (3.181–52.170)	< 0.001	6.262 (1.526–25.693)	0.011
pN stage	N1, N2, N3/ N0	6.640 (4.478–9.846)	< 0.001	4.364 (2.874–6.627)	< 0.001
pT stage	T3, T4/T1, T2	3.930 (2.667–5.790)	< 0.001	2.143 (1.424–3.225)	< 0.001
Histological grade	Poor/ Well, Moderate	2.720 (1.577–4.690)	< 0.001	2.02 (1.168–3.495)	0.012
Age	≥60/ <60	1.270 (0.854–1.889)	0.238		
Sex	M/ F	0.933 (0.642–1.355)	0.715		

OSCC: oral squamous cell carcinoma, *P*: *P* value, HR: Hazard ratio, pT: pathology primary tumor, pN: pathology lymph node metastasis, YK classification: Yamamoto-kohama classification

Table 3 Binary logistic regression analysis for presence of distant, pulmonary and bone metastasis.

	standard error	<i>P</i>	OR	95% CI	
				Lower	Upper
Distant metastasis					
pN	0.330	< 0.001	4.562	2.387	8.719
histological grade	0.454	0.01	3.502	3.244	7.902
lung metastasis					
histological grade	0.453	.001	4.276	1.760	10.391
pN	0.351	.001	3.080	1.546	6.133
bone metastasis					
pN	0.315	< 0.001	5.198	2.802	9.644
histological grade	0.453	0.013	3.097	1.273	7.531

P: *P* value, OR: Odds ratio, CI: confidence interval, pN: pathology lymph node metastasis

pulmonary cancer and 40% in bladder cancer [16]. The survival terms of patients with BM of breast cancer and prostate cancer ranged from 19 to 25 months and from 12 to 53 months, respectively [16,17]. Although the frequency of BM in OSCC was less than other cancers, these data indicate that patients of OSCC with BM had shorter survival than patients with the other cancers. BM induces complications such as bone pain, osteoporosis, pathologic fractures, hypercalcemia, bone marrow failure and spinal cord compression. These restrict the activities of patients as well as the activities of daily life (ADL) frequently resulting in further complications. Of note, all patients with BM except one case had metastasis in vertebrae, possibly due to the presence of the Vertebral Venous Plexus (VVP, or Batson plexus). BM is transferred from a venous system and a portal system through a vertebral artery to the spine, cranium, pelvis, rib, and sternum. The vertebral vein has traffic with other venous systems. VVP is characterized by valve-less vessels and plexus

anastomosis with epidural, thoracic, and abdominal venous. Because the pressure of the blood flow at VVP is near zero the circulating tumor cells could remain in the plexus and later easily infiltrate the vertebrae [18].

Cell adhesion molecules (CAMs) play a major role in several physiological phenomena such as cell differentiation, proliferation and morphology; including the relationship with immunological phenomena such as inflammation and blood coagulation as well as pathological phenomena such as cell malignancy [19]. Heterogeneous expression of CAM is proposed to play an important role for DM in various types of cancer [20]. Cadherin (CDH), which is a transmembrane protein, is a major CAM. They are synthesized as polypeptides and undergo many post-translational modifications to become proteins that mediate cell-cell adhesion and recognition. Among them, E-CDH, the most thoroughly studied member of the CDH family, works as CAM of epithelial cells. Down-regulation or

heterogeneous expression of E-CDH is reported to relate to the invasiveness and metastasis of malignant epithelial tumors in the stomach [21], liver [22], prostate [23], breast [24], esophagus [20], colon [25] and oral cavity [26], respectively. Low expression of E-CDH is suggested to cause disruption of cell-cell adhesive contacts, resulting in the invasion and metastasis of cancer cells. In contrast, over-expression of OB-CDH is reported to relate to bone metastasis of breast and prostate cancers [27, 28]. OB-CDH was firstly found in cell line cells of osteoblast, MC3T3–E1, and expressed in osteoblast and stromal cells of bone marrow [27]. The different expression pattern of OB-CDH compared to the low expression of E-CDH is suggested to be because cancer cells with over-expression of OB-CDH could easily contact stromal cells of bone marrow [27]. It is important to disclose the basic mechanism of metastasis of OSCC and its clinical relevance.

In summary, advanced T stage, positive N stage, lower grade of histologic grade and higher score YK classification were the independent significant prognostic factors of OSCC. Histological grades and pN were the highest prognostic factors for the presence of PM and BM, respectively. BM was found in 5% and all patients with BM except one case had metastasis in vertebrae.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

None declared

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